

Radiation Pattern Shaping using Generalized Luneburg Lenses for Automotive RADAR Antennas

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Abstract—This paper introduces an approach using the Generalized Luneburg Lens as a modular design element to shape automotive RADAR antennas at mmWave frequencies. An optimization routine that includes unwanted effects associated with manufacturing constraints is presented by adding mechanical constraints in the lens design and using a full-wave solver with the feeding antenna. Two lenses are designed; the first increases the directivity from 14.1 to 15.7 dBi, while the second increases the HPBW of the antenna from 57.6 to 129.6 degrees, demonstrating the flexibility of the presented approach.

Index Terms—Antennas, mmWave, Lenses, Automotive RADAR.

I. INTRODUCTION

The European Commission adopted the Vision Zero and Safe System approach in 2018 [1]. The aim is to eliminate deaths and serious injuries on European roads by 2030. Advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) are developed rapidly to assist the driver using various sensors around the vehicle. One of the sensors typically used for functions such as automated emergency braking and blind spot detection is the automotive RADAR. To increase the performance of the RADAR system, waveguide antennas have received a lot of attention in recent years due to their low losses at millimeter wave (mmWave) frequencies. Moreover, to deploy these advanced systems on the road, the antenna solutions must be robust and allow high-volume production. As demonstrated in [2], gapwaveguide antennas meet these requirements while offering all the benefits that come with properly designed metallic waveguides, taking into account manufacturing constraints in the design process.

A. Lens on Antenna (LoA)

Unfortunately, the design of waveguide antennas becomes a highly complex task when many parameters ought to be optimized for a given antenna. This limits the flexibility of waveguide antennas, resulting in substantial engineering effort to adapt the antenna for different sensors. An alternative to waveguide antennas is lens-based solutions [3], where the Luneburg lens has gained much attention. The Luneburg lens offers high directivity combined with low scan losses. However, these solutions are typically rather large in terms of wavelength. Moreover, these solutions have fixed beams

and cannot use the co-located MIMO array typically used for Automotive RADAR. Alternatively, lenses can be used in combination with existing antennas. This way, the lens can increase the antenna's performance while staying compact to use in MIMO arrays. Conformal Transformation Optics have been used to increase the directivity [4] or reduce the ripple on the pattern [5]. One of the difficulties for such solutions is the need for anisotropic metamaterials when applying a transformation in 3D. However, these anisotropic metamaterials cannot be made with simple dielectrics and need complex, partially metallic, sub-wavelength structures, which are expensive to manufacture at a larger scale. Therefore, we aim to use a purely dielectric lens for the approach presented in the next sections. This allows the lens to be 3D printed.

II. GENERALIZED LUNEBURG LENS

The Luneburg lens [6] has gained great interest in recent years with the advancements in the field of metamaterials [7, 8] as well as similar lenses using geodesics [9]. Although the Luneburg lens is matched to free space at its edge, placing feeding elements at the edge can be problematic. Two of these problems are the mutual coupling between feeding elements and obstruction of the radiation at far angles. The Generalized Luneburg Lens (GLL) [10] solves these problems by placing the feeding antennas further away from the edge of the lens, increasing the distance between them and reducing the obstruction of the propagating wave at far angles.

A. Non-isotropic Feeding

Another advantage of the GLL is that it does not need a point source at the edge of the lens. This is due to the distance allowed between the feeding elements and the edge of the lens. As a result, the impinging wavefront onto the lens does not need to be circular but can be flatter. Such a wavefront mimics a point-like feeding element further away from the lens, as is typical for the GLL.

III. LENS ON ANTENNA (LOA) DESIGN

As discussed in section II-A, the GLL can be used with non-isotropic antennas. Moreover, it is possible to place the feeding antenna away from the edge of the lens. Using this, two designs will be presented where GLL's are used to shape the radiation pattern of the antenna. With the aim at mmWave automotive RADAR, a gapwaveguide antenna was chosen with

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of using a generalized Luneburg lens for increased directivity.

specifications one may find for automotive RADAR at 76 to 77 GHz. This type of antenna was chosen due to its low losses at the frequency of operation as well as its robustness concerning manufacturing. The antenna is designed and functions very similar to a standard slotted ridge gapwaveguide antenna as described in [11], However the specific design could not be shared in this paper. Nevertheless, the concept presented is not limited to this type of antenna and can be applied to different feeding antennas.

1) *Increasing the Directivity*: Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of one of two studied LoA configurations. In this example, the aim is to enhance antenna directivity. The non-ideal directivity is illustrated by the curved phase front in red. A generalized Luneburg can align the antenna phase front at the top of the lens to increase the directivity.

2) *Increasing the Field of View*: Not only could the GLL be used to increase the directivity of an antenna, Figure 2 shows a schematic representation of how one may use a combination of two GLLs to increase the Field of view (FoV) of the antenna. In this diagram, only a section of the rays is shown of the antenna, which carries most of the energy radiated. With this configuration, these rays are bent away from the broadside direction.

IV. MMWAVE LENS DESIGN

Due to the small wavelength within the frequency band of operation, manufacturing constraints must be considered while designing and optimizing the LoA. Although additive manufacturing techniques have become more accurate over the last few years, SLA 3D printing is one of the few technologies that can create the required size for these lenses. Therefore,

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram of using two generalized Luneburg lenses for increased Field of View.

the presented lenses are designed with SLA printing as the assumed technique, using the Radix™Printable Dielectric material from Rogers corporation as the material of choice. This is chosen because of the possibility of printing small feature sizes and the low dielectric loss.

A. Gradient Index Unit Cell

A unit cell is created to implement the different dielectric constants seen in the GLLs, as shown in Figure 3. The effective dielectric constant

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{\epsilon_r w + \epsilon_0(p - w)}{p} \quad (1)$$

can be calculated from the dielectric constant of the used material ϵ_r , the width of the unit cell p , the width of the material w , and the dielectric constant of free space ϵ_0 . To achieve an effective dielectric constant which is locally isotropic $p \ll \lambda$, however, this is not possible given the constraints from manufacturing. Fortunately, p can be taken relatively large $p \approx \lambda/3$ without compromising the effectiveness of the GLL. Moreover, the effects of the larger unit cell are included in the optimization since the lens is optimized with a full-wave solver.

B. Optimization

As mentioned in Section IV-A, the LoA design was optimized using a full-wave solver. For the optimization, no changes were made in the feeding antenna. The dielectric profile of the lens was indirectly controlled using control points as depicted in Figure 3. The control points are placed equidistant along the unit cell of the GLL, along the y -direction of the antenna. The shape of the unit cell is then

Fig. 3: Schematic representation of the unit-cell for the generalized Luneburg lens

obtained by interpolating these control points using splines. Splines were chosen since SLA printing cannot create sharp corners below the allowable feature size. The outer control point was also forced to be greater than 0.2mm to ensure a mechanical connection between the unit cells. With these constraints in place, the control points and the position of the GLLs relative to the antenna in the x - and z -direction were optimized using the Nelder Mead algorithm in CST Studio Suite 2023. Within this optimization, two lenses are designed to increase the directivity or the Half Power Beam Width (HPBW) as much as possible given the mechanical constraints, the used material, and the given feeding antenna.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the two optimization results on top of the feeding gapwaveguide antenna. Figure 4. (a) shows the 'Directivity lens' used to increase the directivity and 4.(b) shows the design for increased FoV.

A. Radiation patterns

Figure 5 shows the radiation pattern along the azimuth plane for the different LoA designs. Together with the patterns of the lens, the pattern is shown of the antenna without any lens. These results show that the 'FoV lens' increases the FoV from an HPBW of 57.6 to 129.6 degrees. The 'Directivity lens' increases the directivity from 14.1 dBi to 15.7 dBi. The antenna was designed with a low reflection coefficient $S_{11} < -17$ dB from 76 to 77 GHz, which remained below -17 dB with the addition of the lenses.

B. Field Propagation

To visualize the performance of the LoA design of the Directivity lens, the phase of the Magnetic fields is shown in Fig. 6. The phase is taken from the y -component of the magnetic field at a crosscut in the center of the antenna. The phase propagation at the top of the lens shows that the phase

(a) Directivity lens

(b) FoV lens

Fig. 4: Optimized lens on antenna designs

Fig. 5: Azimuth pattern of the optimized lens on antenna design.

distribution is more flat than that of the feeding antenna. To visualize the Impact of the FoV lens, the amplitude of the magnetic field is taken at the same crosscut, shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that the magnetic field is propagating towards further angles in the azimuth plane.

From the results shown in Fig. 5, it can be seen that the proposed design successfully modified the radiation patterns of the antennas using GLLs. Besides this, the nature of the GLL allows the lens to be offset from the feeding antenna, eliminating the loading effect of the dielectric lens, resulting in a reflection coefficient that does not significantly change. This method allows radiation characteristics to be modified modularly and optimized by changing the GLLs above the antenna. Moreover, the use of 3D printing allows for rapid prototyping.

The achieved radiation patterns are not beyond the scope

(a) Phase propagation of the lens on antenna design with the directivity increasing lens.

(b) Phase propagation of feeding gapwaveguide antenna.

Fig. 6: Comparison of the phase propagation of the TM-polarization at the center of the antenna for the lens on antenna design and the antenna without lens.

(a) Magnetic field amplitude of lens on antenna design with the Field of view increasing lens.

(b) Magnetic field amplitude of feeding gapwaveguide antenna.

Fig. 7: Comparison of the Magnetic field amplitude at the center of the antenna for the lens on antenna design and the antenna without a lens.

of what waveguide antennas can achieve. However, this novel method allows us to change the radiation pattern with a large reduction in the design process. One of the potential benefits of this approach is the reduction of the surface current for the 'FoV lens' compared to the traditional waveguide antenna with similar FoV. An indication can be seen due to the low field amplitude along the top of the feeding antenna in Fig. 7. Lower surface current typically increases the consistency of radiation patterns when placed in an array and increases isolation between radiating elements; however, more investigation needs to be done to verify this.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates a novel approach for using generalized Luneburg lenses to modify the radiation performance of automotive radar antennas. With consideration of available materials and mechanical constraints taken into account, two sets of lenses are designed. Different combinations of Luneburg lenses demonstrated that it is possible to increase the directivity of the reference antenna or increase the HPBW in the azimuth plane of the antenna. This was achieved without increasing the reflection coefficient of the antenna above its target specification of -17 dB.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been funded by the H2020-MSCA Project 955629 ITN-5VC and supported by funding from ELLIIT strategic research.

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